

TRANSNATURE

Data Management Plan

Deliverable 6.4

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The Project

The governance of transboundary biodiversity is a complex issue that is largely understudied in Europe. TRANSNATURE aims to fill this gap by addressing three research questions:

1. To what extent and how do transboundary conservation areas involve different types of managing authorities and stakeholders in effective governance mechanisms to enhance conservation?
2. To what extent and how does the stratification of different governance mechanisms in the same natural areas, such as World Heritage sites, European Groupings of Territorial Cooperation (EGTCs), national management authorities, subnational authorities and indigenous and community conserved areas, trigger processes that strengthen biodiversity conservation? Are there cooperation mechanisms or mechanisms of conflict resolution in place among the different actors involved?
3. To what extent can transboundary conservation areas contribute to stop ecological degradation by improving the prevention of both cross-border pollution and transnational wildlife crime in the EU?

To respond to these questions, the project will analyze in detail and compare the following case studies: (1) ZASNET EGTC and transboundary biosphere reserve Meseta Ibérica (Spain/Portugal); (2) Parco Naturale delle Prealpi Giulie and Triglavski Narodni Park (Italy/Slovenia) (3) Westerschelde (Netherlands/Belgium); (4) Baltic to Barents (Finland/Sweden/Norway). These cases share a number of fundamental features (European cases of transboundary conservation areas featuring multi-level and multi-actor governance) but at the same time ensure enough variation (different European regions, different ecosystems, different kinds of authorities involved). Desk research on relevant legal and policy documents adopted at different governance levels (international, European, national, and sub-national) will be combined with semi-structured interviews of and focus groups with key stakeholders (empirical research method), as well as with a small component of ethnographic research.

TRANSNATURE will contribute to policymaking at the international, European, national and conservation area levels, since it has repercussions on the CBD post-2020 global biodiversity framework, the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, the Fit for 55 Package under the European Green Deal as well as national biodiversity strategies and the management regulations of the study areas included in the project. Policy impact is ensured through a specific stakeholder engagement plan. The specific transnational added value of the project is that it compares cases that would be otherwise studied in isolation.

TRANSNATURE aims to identify innovative governance models for biodiversity protection and stakeholder engagement, distill common governance principles and highlight best practices in study areas that are more advanced concerning aspects of transnational, vertical and horizontal cooperation.

I Data Management Plan Framework

1.1 Timeline and Template

The present Data Management Plan (DMP) is considered deliverable 6.4 (D6.4) of the project and will be finalized during month six of the project (August 2023). It was drafted following Biodiversa+ guidelines. The suggested template was adapted to the project's peculiarities. It will be updated during the project's life, where need be.

II Data Management Plan

1.2 Data Managers

Overall management and lead of the TRANSNATURE consortium is taken by Eurac Research. This includes the drafting of the Data Management Plan, coordination of data exchange among partners. The project foresees a 3-level storage plan, explained in further sections of this Data Management Plan. Each partner has a focal point for data management, who is tasked to coordinate within the relevant offices, colleagues and with Eurac Research.

Eurac Research' Data Management Expert as well as a dedicated project focal point will take care of the overall consortium data management.

The present document is stored in the project's Teams folder, accessible anytime to all project partners. Guiding principles of the project data and this plan are Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse (FAIR principles).

Following are the relevant contacts for the consortium.

Eurac Research - Data Management Expert	Liise Lehtsalu	Liise.Lehtsalu@eurac.edu
Eurac Research - Project Data Management	Martina Gianola	Martina.gianola@eurac.edu
University Rovira i Virgili - Data Management Focal person	Maria Marquès Banqué	maria.marques@urv.cat
Ghent University - Data Management Focal person	Hendrik Schoukens	Hendrik.Schoukens@UGent.be
University of Lapland - Data Management Focal person	Nuccio Mazzullo	nuccio.mazzullo@ulapland.fi

1.3 Data Identification and Description

1.3.1. Purpose of Research

This project will showcase and compare selected transboundary governance models for biodiversity conservation in Europe, with the objectives to: 1) identify successful examples of transboundary biodiversity conservation, 2) propose ways to address common challenges and effectively protect biodiversity, and 3) elaborate policy recommendations to improve the effectiveness of transboundary biodiversity conservation governance.

1.3.2. Project Data

The outputs of long-term value include metadata collection of relevant scholarly literature, metadata collection of legal documents, methods of qualitative data collection, production of anonymized interview

and focus group reports and production of policy recommendations. For outputs being published, see section 1.8.

Data collected and generated for this research is:

Data	Format	Reuse and source	Duration of collection
Scholarly literature	Textual data	Yes - e.g. Web of Science, Scopus, books	Whole project duration, mainly during desk research and during WP4 (year 3)
Metadata collection of scholarly literature and legal documents	Interoperable formats suitable for Citavi	Same as above	Whole project duration
Legal and policy texts	Textual data	Yes - e.g., EUR-Lex, UNTS, ECOLEX, Aranzadi Instituciones, CENDOJ	Whole project duration, mainly during desk research (first project phase)
Statistical data	Numerical data, quantitative	Yes - statistical databases (animal population statistics)	Whole project duration
<i>Generated:</i>			
Interviews	Video and audio recordings, transcriptions, interview reports, textual data	n/a	Mainly in year 2 (WP 2 and 3)
Focus groups	Video or audio recordings, transcriptions, reports, textual data	n/a	Mainly in year 2 (WP 2 and 3)
Maps and illustrations	Image and graphic data	n/a	Whole project duration, mainly at the beginning and at the end of the project (years 1 and 3)
Physical notes of the interview	Textual data	n/a	Mainly in year 2
Photos of mind maps	Image	n/a	Mainly in year 2 (WP 2 and 3)
Photos during stakeholder engagement and focus groups	Image and graphic data	n/a	Mainly in year 2 (WP 2 and 3)

No physical outputs apart from interview notes are foreseen at this stage of the project. A detailed list of file formats can be found in section 1.6.

Given the different above-mentioned dimensions covered by the research and the fact that each WP has a different thematic focus, the expected size of data generated and re-used can be defined only at a later stage of the project.

All data will directly or indirectly serve the end goal of drafting policy recommendations and might be useful to other local governments, researchers, university students, policy makers and citizens.

1.4 Data Organization and Exchange

This paragraph refers to data organization and exchange during the project.

Desk research on relevant legal and policy documents adopted at different governance levels will be combined with semi-structured interviews and focus groups gathering key stakeholders. Interviews and focus groups will take place in each case study. Interviewees will be selected with a view to covering the major groups of stakeholders. Interview data will be used to develop the themes to be explored in the focus groups and will be later examined through legal analytical approaches. Focus groups, which will involve 6 to 8 participants per study area and will include a green criminology approach, will gather participants' experiences and beliefs about the governance of transboundary conservation areas and its role in pollution and wildlife crime. Differently from interviews, in focus groups results will emerge from the interaction of the stakeholders involved. Interviews and focus groups will be recorded, transcribed, anonymized, and safely stored (see section 8 below). Interview and focus groups' datasets will be analyzed to respond to RQ1, RQ2, and RQ3.

Data accessibility will occur on three levels:

<i>Location</i>	<i>Type of Data</i>	<i>Notes</i>	<i>Accessibility</i>
Partners' Institutional Storage	Raw data (incl. interview recordings and original transcripts) Working drafts	Data will be shared on project Teams once elaborated into a working draft, or for data containing identifiable information (such as interviews) once pseudonymized.	Accessible only among researchers of the same institution. Data security measures foreseen by the partners' institutions must be followed.
TRANSNATURE Microsoft Teams/SharePoint	Project documentation Literature and/or bibliographies Data processed for analysis Working drafts Pseudonymized data	It is meant to be a space for communication, collaboration, sharing of material and literature, and short-term data storing. Each deliverable or other output and related data used for the creation of such shall be uploaded in the WP-Teams folder. Data related to human research subjects (e.g., interviews, focus groups, notes of observations) can be shared in pseudonymized form but only through this dedicated workspace. The pseudonymization keys must stay with the partners.	Accessible to partners and project collaborators only. For each new addition of project team members, Eurac Project Coordinator shall be informed. Each collaborator shall work in his/her WP folder only. Access to other Work Package folders is allowed but should be limited for research or coordination purposes. Under no circumstance editing, renaming, or moving files of a Work Package folder other than the own is allowed, unless previously agreed with the respective Work Package leader.

Zenodo (repository)	Project outcomes Analyzed data Literature and/or bibliographies Anonymized interview and focus group data Statistical data	A dedicated project community will be set up on Zenodo , for long-term storage of data; Data related to human research subjects will occur only in anonymized form, as stated in the Ethics Plan.*	Accessible to everyone on the world wide web. No registration to access needed. Data will be uploaded once approved by the partners.
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*The University of Lapland will adopt a discipline-specific approach for ethnographic data, proposed by the European Association of Social Anthropologists. The default for the data is not anonymizing but acknowledging the intellectual property of the authors by keeping data in their name unless they explicitly consent for anonymizing. Embargo and confidentiality over materials that cannot be anonymized will be kept. Please find more in the Annex 1 of this document.

Data saved in the team folder shall be easily findable and distinguishable by each collaborator and organized by work package. The suggested file naming convention for newly produced documents of this project is the following: *Clear title_draft version_date of last change*. Reviewers of documents shall add *_rev+initials* and different versions of documents clearly marked. Literature should be saved as follows: *year of publication_surname of author_additional surname if multiple authors or et al_short title of contribution*. Legal/policy documents should be named as follows *_name of the document_year of adoption*.

Data Quality

Quality assurance processes will be further developed during the project and will in any case respect the minimum standards set in the project's Ethics Plan. At current stage, WPs conducting literature review are following criteria and guidelines set out by each WP leader, also by using internationally recognized tools such as electronic databases (Web of Science, Scopus). Interview and focus group guides will be developed in the common methodology (title 'Research design TRANSNATURE (Biodiversa+)').

Accessibility of data collected through human research subjects is subject to their consent to the publishing of their data. Latter can be withdrawn. In such a case, no further data will be collected, and any data related to the participant already collected and not yet anonymized will be destroyed (see Ethics Plan).

1.5 Data Storage and Back-up

During the project's implementation, data will be stored in the locations mentioned in section 1.4.

a) **Partners institutional storage:** It is the responsibility of the Work Package leaders and institutions' Data Management Experts and Protection Officers to ensure that this might be an institutional, safe, and backed-up workspace, that allows data recovery. It is also their duty to ensure that personal data and related documentation are processed and stored in an ethical as well as in a way that is compliant with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and national laws.

One partner, University Rovira i Virgili (URV) uses OneDrive for storage. Real-time version control is provided by the URV's DMS (Document Management System), i.e., Microsoft One Drive, that has the following technical characteristics:

University of Lapland will use eduuni platform for text and photos storage. This has proved useful in a previous project. Audio and video files will be backed up on the CSC.fi (Centre for Computer Science - IT Centre for Science) servers.

Eurac Research will exchange and store data directly in the project Microsoft Teams. Storage details can be found in the next paragraph. Within the Microsoft Teams, private channels will be created for identifiable data, with restricted access. The WP6 management folder of the project Teams is already accessible only to management staff of this project.

University of Ghent: will set up a Teams folder for the information gathered by UGent for the project. This will be backed up by UGent Cloud.

b) **Microsoft Teams** is covered by Eurac institutional backup. All data on Eurac Research systems (on premise, cloud) are backed up daily and are subject to a long-term retention policy. The backups are stored separately from data. Eurac Research is ISO27001 certified, and all backup procedures are compliant with ISO27001 and audited yearly.

1.6 Data Sharing, Standards and Metadata

Below a list of file formats used during the project:

Data type	Format	Notes
Textual data	.pdf or .odf .docx Physical data (book) .rtf	.docx only for text processing during the project, no long-term storage (meaning uploads on Zenodo should occur in .pdf or .odf version);
Statistical data	.csv .exe	
Pictures	.tiff (preferred) .jpeg .png .jpg	
Audios	.mp3 .wav .wmf	WAVE in case of long-term storage
Video	.mp4 .mpeg .mov	

No standards will be used, but all files are saved in formats (mentioned above) known and common to all partners. The only software planned to use for accessing and use data is Nvivo or MaxQDA for interview transcription. Furthermore, audio/video data of University of Lapland will be stored as .wav/.mpeg files respectively, according to the standards of the International Association of Sound and Audiovisual Archives (IASA-TC 05, Handling and Storage of Audio and Video Carriers).

Metadata

As mentioned above, data will be made publicly available in the dedicated Zenodo project community. For each uploaded data, following metadata will be created: publication type and date, title, authors, description, access right, license, language, keywords. The team is considering the use of controlled vocabularies. When relevant, qualified references¹ will be included in (meta)data. Zenodo metadata fields include the element "related identifiers" which will be used when appropriate.

With regards to ethnographic data, if produced, University of Lapland will proceed as follows: Considering that ethnographic data must be agreed with each interviewee, the partner shall produce own metadata for those type of data online - in the form of a README file. They will be stored with CSC in Finland.

Methodology and tools will be shared alongside data whenever possible, or otherwise clearly described in README files deposited together with data. README files will include information about methodology (e.g., participant recruitment, interview/focus group/survey design, decisions taken during data analysis, tools used for data analysis), reference to software needed to access data, unit of measurements, data cleaning. No specific data documentation standards will be followed.

1.7 Data Restrictions

Data	Restriction	Data sharing
Interview data Focus group data	Yes, since the interviewee could be identifiable, unless interviewees consent to be publicly cited	Personal data will be stored by the partner producing them. Pseudonymized interview data will be shared among partners. Anonymized data will be made publicly accessible on Zenodo.
Personal data indigenous participants	Same as above	Same as above
Secondary literature	Yes, due to Intellectual Property Rights	Bibliographies will be shared among partners

Further details of sensitive/personal/restricted data management can be found in the project's ethics plan.

As mentioned above, concerning ethnographic data, University of Lapland will adopt the approach outlined in Annex 1.

1.8 Data Publishing and Licensing

Project data will be published on Zenodo, that functions also as a repository. A dedicated community will be created, please find more information in section 1.9.

No embargo periods for published data are foreseen. License will be CC0 or CC-BY.

¹ Qualified references include crossreferencing to other project outputs or datasets. The two datasets will then be linked. Explanatory, practical examples of this will be given in a second stage of the project.
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Open Access

Open Access practices can be defined only at a second stage of this project since the publisher will be chosen only once the project results are available.

1.9 Data Archiving

Data selected for long-term storage (lasting after the projects ending), will be deposited in the repository Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>), where a project-specific community is created. The repository assigns DOIs to data and the persistent identifiers resolve to the digital objects which they identify. For file sizes below 50GB per record, no specific arrangements are necessary to deposit in Zenodo. Should partners use institutional repositories for long-term storage, data will not be duplicated in Zenodo but a metadata record for those data will also be included in the project Zenodo Community. Data deposited in Zenodo can be found via direct searches on Zenodo but, more importantly, Zenodo is also harvested by scientific aggregators, including for example openAIRE and DataCite Commons. If access to some data needs to be restricted for whatever reason, the metadata of those data remain available and findable in Zenodo. No embargo periods for data are foreseen at this stage of the project. This can differ for ethnographic data of University of Lapland (see annex 1).

Data will be uploaded during the project and will be useable by third parties also after the end of the project. The project Zenodo Community will be curated by the project Coordinator for 3 years after the end of the project.

At this stage, no time limit is foreseen for the long-term preservation of the data.

1.10 Costs

Given that all data storages used in TRANSNATURE (Teams, Zenodo) are used for free or already covered by either by partner's institutions or project overheads, there are no additional project costs foreseen. The only costs occurring indirectly are the data management and community curation human resources' costs. The Project Management Team is responsible for the data management together with each institutions focal point, backed by the respective competent support offices of their home institutions.

Annex 1

EASA's Statement on Data Governance in Ethnographic Projects¹

This statement describes some of the core methodical and ethical practices of ethnographic research.² These practices have implications for the norms and forms of data management in ethnography.³ We issue this statement to help ethnographers respond to current mandates for data archiving, storage, and sharing from governments, universities, and funders.

This statement places ethnographic research within the special clause on “academic expression” included in Article 85(2) of the GDPR. This derogation has been designed to guarantee the critical social value of humanities and social sciences research. We call on universities, funders, and academic institutions to fully execute and implement this special clause in the case of ethnographic research.

1. **Ownership:** Ethnographic materials are coproduced by researchers and research participants and are embedded in particular social contexts. As such, they cannot be fully owned or controlled by researchers, research participants or third parties. The use of standard intellectual property licenses and protocols may not apply to all ethnographic materials.
2. **Archiving:** In ethnographic research “data” are always part of a social relationship. It is not easily reducible to a fixed and finished product. As such, it may not always be possible to archive or store research materials. In other cases, the archiving of ethnographic materials will require specific technical features (e.g. different roles for access, editing, sharing or privacy) not available in most institutional repositories.
3. **Consent:** Ethnographic participation in a social milieu can lead to situations and dynamics that are not always controllable by researchers and for which it is not always possible (indeed, it is often impossible) to obtain prior informed consent. Moreover, since research materials are never completely fixed, written consent can never fully determine its future uses or interpretations as “data”. In contexts of violence or vulnerability, written consent may violate research participants’ privacy and confidentiality, and even put them at risk. For ethnographers, informed consent is an ongoing process.
4. **Custodianship:** Researchers have a scientific and ethical responsibility to preserve and protect the integrity of ethnographic materials. This is a responsibility that is usually negotiated with research participants. These forms of custodianship, caretaking or archiving cannot always be anticipated or pre-formatted.
5. **Embargo:** Researchers have a special duty to consider controlling third party access to ethnographic materials and retain the rights of embargo and confidentiality over those materials that cannot be anonymized or turned into data entries.
6. **Public access and sharing:** The collaborative nature of ethnographic research implies that ethnographers have a special duty to consider requests by research participants (or their descendants) to share materials, unless this actively and unnecessarily harms (some of) them. Ethnographers also have a duty to consider appropriate ways of making research materials publicly accessible when this will not violate ethical principles of ethnographic research. Making such materials accessible may require special technical features not available in most institutional repositories.

¹ This statement is based on the Leiden Statement on Data Management and Anthropology, as published in Pels et al. (2018) *Data Management in Anthropology: The Next Phase in Ethics Governance?* *Social Anthropology/Anthropologie sociale* 26/3: 1-23.

² See the [Principles of Professional Responsibility](#) (2012) of the American Anthropological Association and the [Ethical Guidelines for Good Research Practice](#) (2011) of the Association of Social Anthropologists.

³ For an example of a data governance framework for ethnographic research, see Corsín Jiménez, A. (2018) [Data Governance Framework for Ethnography v 1.0](#), Madrid: CSIC.